

Contraceptive Use among Women of Reproductive Age in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Effective use of modern methods of contraception remains a key strategy of preventing unintended pregnancies thereby contributing to the reduction of maternal deaths. This study was aimed at assessing the ever use, methods and side effects of modern contraceptives used by women of reproductive age. It was a cross-sectional study done among women who were evaluated at a private health facility in Makurdi. Data was collected through a self-administered pre-tested questionnaire. SPSS version-25 was used for data entry and analysis. Results showed that the average age of respondents were 32.6 ± 6.0 . Majority (65.1%) had tertiary education, married (91.7%) and are Christians (97.0%). Participants that have ever used modern contraceptives were 60.7% of the 239 participants. Among these; 77.2% had used male condom, 12.4% Combined Oral Contraceptives (COC), 5.5% injectable, 2.1% Emergency oral contraceptives (EOC), 1.4% intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD), 0.7% implanon and 0.7% female condom. Majority (69.0%) did not experience any complications. Others experienced irregular vaginal bleeding (13.1%), lower abdominal pains (6.9%), high blood pressure (3.4%), and vaginal discharge (2.7%) among others. Contraceptive use was high with the male condom being the commonest method and fewer side effects. Consistent efforts are needed to ensure sustained utilization of modern methods of contraceptives.

Keywords: Contraceptive, Male condom, Maternal death, Pregnancy, Unmet need

INTRODUCTION

Globally, about 529,000 women die from pregnancy-related causes every year and approximately 99% of these maternal deaths occur in developing nations¹. Nigeria is said to be the most populous black nation in the world with an estimated population at over 190 million

and projected to increase by 44% between 2015 and 2030². Although, the country contributes 2.5% to the world population, it is believed to account for 14% of maternal deaths worldwide every year^{3,4}. The Nigeria Demographic Health Survey (NDHS) of 2018 puts her maternal

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mortality ratio at 512 per 100,000 live births with regional variations, the worse which is over 1000 deaths per 100,000 live births in the north-eastern part of the country. .

One of the key strategies in reducing maternal deaths is promoting the uptake of modern methods of contraceptives. Several efforts have been made towards commodity provision, availability and affordability, but utilization has been a challenge in many parts of the country. The NDHS of 2018 reports the use of any method of contraceptive to be 17% and use of modern method to be 12%.² This has obviously impacted negatively on maternal health because effective and consistent use of modern methods of contraceptives were certainly help reduce the incidence of unwanted pregnancies which ends up in induced abortions with its sequelae, as well as help women achieve reasonable child spacing and minimize family size. The overall gains are for the individual woman, family, society and nation at large.^{5, 6} Some of the challenges to utilization of modern methods of contraceptives have been culture, religion, myths, opposition by male partner, lack of awareness, fear of side effects and economy among others have been receiving attention by major stakeholders.^{6, 7, 8} It is hoped that uptake will gradually improve with time if these efforts to promote utilization are sustained. This study was aimed at assessing the proportion of the study population who has ever used any modern method of contraceptives, choice of method and side effect profile among them. The findings will help in further guiding the strategies of the campaign towards enhancing usage of the methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was a cross-sectional survey of 239 women who were undergoing evaluation for clinical infertility at a private health facility (Musafaha diagnostic Centre) in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. Respondents who were informed about the study and gave consent were recruited while those who declined consent were

excluded. The questionnaire was divided into sections namely: socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, methods of contraceptives used and side effect profile. Data was collected using a self-administered pre-tested questionnaire and entered into SPSS software version 25.

The sample size was determined using the Fisher's formula; $N = z^2 p q / d^2$

$z =$ standard normal deviate corresponding to level of significance at 95% = 1.96, $p =$ prevalence of modern methods of contraceptive use by women of reproductive age in Nigeria = 12% (0.12), $q = 1 - P$ (0.88), $d =$ level of precision, set at 5% = 0.05; So $N = (1.96)^2 \times 0.12 \times 0.88 / (0.05)^2 = 162$. However, the sample size was raised to 239 to make provision for non-responses.

RESULTS

The most prevalent age group was those who were 30 years or less (38.9%). However, the average age of all the respondents was 32.6 ± 6.0 years. Majority (65.1%) had tertiary education, 17.1% had secondary, 12.1% had primary and 6.7% had no formal education. Majority were married (91.7%), 7.1% were single, 0.8% divorced and 0.4% co-habiting. Applicants/un-employed constituted 66.5%, farmers 15.5%, civil servants 14.2% and traders 3.8%. Majority were Christians (97.0%), 1.3% Muslims and 1.7% other religion. Among the ethnic groups, Tiv were 68.2%, Idoma 13.4%, Ibo 9.2%, Hausa/Fulani 5.0%, Igede 2.1%, Yoruba 1.7% and others 0.4% (See table 1). Ever use of a modern method of contraceptive by the respondents studied was 60.7%. Among these; 77.2% had used male condom, 12.4% COC, 5.5% injectable, 2.1% EOC, 1.4% IUCD, 0.7% implanon and 0.7% female condom (See table 2). Majority (69.0%) did not experience any complications. Others experienced irregular vaginal bleeding (13.1%), lower abdominal pains (6.9%), high blood pressure (3.4%), and vaginal discharge (2.7%) among others (See table 3)

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variables	Number (239)	Percentage (100%)
Age		
≤30	93	38.9
31-34	76	31.5
35-39	46	19.2
40-44	20	8.4
≥45	4	1.7
Education		
None	16	6.7
Primary	29	12.1
Secondary	41	17.1
Tertiary	153	64.1
Occupation		
Trading	9	3.8
Civil servants	34	14.2
Farmers	37	15.5
Others	159	66.5
Marital Status		
Co-habiting	1	0.4
Divorce	2	0.8
Single	17	7.1
Married	219	91.7
Ethnicity		
Others	1	0.4
Yoruba	4	1.7
Igede	5	2.1
Hausa/Fulani	12	5.0
Ibo	22	9.2
Idoma	32	13.4
Tiv	163	68.2
Religion		
Islam	3	1.3
Others	4	1.7
Christianity	232	97.0

Table 2: Contraceptive usage by the respondents

Contraceptive	Number (239)	Percentage (100%)
Yes	145	60.7
No	94	39.3
Method Use	Number (145)	Percentage (100%)
Female Condom	1	0.7
Implanon	1	0.7
IUCD	2	1.4
Emergency contraceptives	3	2.1
Injectable	8	5.5
Combine oral pills	18	12.4
Male Condom	112	77.2

Key: IUCD (Intrauterine contraceptive device)

Table3: Complications following contraceptive use

Complications	Number(145)	Percentage (100%)
Others	2	1.4
Pregnancy	2	1.4
Weight gain	3	2.1
Vaginal discharge	4	2.7
Hypertension	5	3.4
Abdominal pains	10	6.9
Irregular vaginal bleeding	19	13.1
None	100	69.0

DISCUSSION

The study reports a high (60.7%) ever used of modern methods of contraceptive among the women; although the overall contraceptive usage for all methods and modern methods in Nigeria is as low as 17% and 12% respectively.² It has been reported that as much as 60% of married women of childbearing age globally use contraceptive methods.⁹ This finding is in keeping with global statistics. This could be due to the fact that majority of the women were not only married but had tertiary level of education and were urban dwellers. The 2018 NDHS reported that contraceptive usage was more among women who were married, urban dwellers and had more than secondary education.¹⁰

This finding is not surprising due to the fact that majority of the women had tertiary level of education and hence were well enlightened of the benefit of contraceptive usage.⁹ In recent times awareness through enlightenment campaigns, debates, advertisements and public health talks have increased tremendously.^{10, 11} Social media, electronic/print media, campaigns in schools, religious and traditional institutions have helped in information dissemination very widely.¹² Women are beginning to appreciate the benefits of contraceptive usage in preventing unwanted pregnancy, sexually transmitted infections (STI), positive contribution towards enhancing family health and economy, reduction in maternal and child mortality and overall national development.^{13, 14}

Among the contraceptives used by the women, the male condom was the commonest, followed by the oral pills and

then injectable method. This is similar to the reports of so many studies done on method usage^{9,14-16}. The dual role of the male condom in preventing pregnancy and STIs as well as its availability and affordability makes it the most commonly used. The social marketing and campaigns by non-governmental organizations (NGOs), social media, health facilities and traditional institutions have helped in promoting condom usage.

One of the factors responsible for the unmet need to modern contraceptives is the fear of side effects. Women chose to delay or discontinue contraceptives due to anticipated or actual experience of side effects by themselves or friends and close confidants. These side effects have been reported to include; irregular menstrual bleeding, headaches, vomiting, nausea, changes in weight and blood pressure.¹⁷⁻²⁰ In our study majority (69.0%) of the women did not report any side effect. However, we found irregular vaginal bleeding, lower abdominal pains, high blood pressure and vaginal discharge among the few complaints.

CONCLUSION

The use of modern methods of contraceptives among the women was high. The side effects observed were however few. Consistent efforts are needed to ensure sustained utilization of modern methods of contraceptives

Recommendations

Enlightenment campaigns towards enhancing utilization of contraceptives should be sustained. Accessibility and affordability of methods should continue to be priority of the health programs by governments and non-governmental organizations. Funding for reproductive health research and health care financing generally must be improved upon.

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Conflict of interest

The author's declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Nour NM. An Introduction to Maternal Mortality. *Reviews Obstet Gynaecol*, 2008; 1(2):77-81.
2. Alo O A, Daini BO, Omisile OK, Ubah EJ, Adelusi OE and Idoko-Asuelimhen O. Factors influencing the use of modern contraceptive in Nigeria: a multilevel logistic analysis using linked data from performance monitoring and accountability 2020. *BMC Women's Health* 2020; 20:191. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-01059-6>. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
3. Meh C, Thind A, Ryan B and Terry A. Levels and determinants of maternal mortality in northern and southern Nigeria. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 2019; 19:417. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-019-2471-8>. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
4. Sageer R, Kongnyuy E, Adebimpe WO, Omosehin O, Ogunsola EA and Sanni B. Causes and contributory factors of maternal mortality: evidence from maternal and perinatal death surveillance and response in Ogun state, Southwest Nigeria. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 2019; 19:63. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-019-2202-1>. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
5. Aina IT, Aina-Pelemo AD. The Use of Contraceptives in Nigeria: Benefits, Challenges and Probable Solutions. *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization* 2019; 86:88-99. Available at: DOI: 10.7176/JLPG. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
6. Blackstone SR and Iwelunmor J. Determinants of contraceptive use among Nigerian couples: evidence from the 2013 Demographic and Health Survey. *Contracept Reprod Med* 2017; 2:9. Available at: DOI 10.1186/s40834-017-0037-6.

- (Accessed 26 February 2021).
7. Ajayi AI, Adeniyi OV and Akpan W. Use of traditional and modern contraceptives among childbearing women: findings from a mixed methods study in two southwestern Nigerian states. *BMC Public Health* 2018; 18:604. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5522-6>. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
 8. Bajoga UA, Atagame KL and Okigbo CC. Media Influence on Sexual Activity and Contraceptive Use: A Cross Sectional Survey among Young Women in Urban Nigeria. *Afri J Reprod Health* 2015; 19 (3): 100-110.
 9. Okpokumoku S E, Nwajei SD and Nwose E U. Sexual Behaviour, Knowledge and Use of Contraceptives among Undergraduate Students. *J Health Sci Res* 2017; 2(2): 10-17. Available at: DOI: 10.18311/jhsr/2017/18113. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
 10. National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] and ICF. 2019. Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018. Abuja, Nigeria, and Rockville, Maryland, USA: NPC and ICF.
 11. Wang C and Cao H. Persisting Regional Disparities in Modern Contraceptive Use and Unmet Need for Contraception among Nigerian Women. *BioMed Research International* Volume 2019, Article ID 9103928, 9 pages. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9103928>. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
 12. Ejembi, CL, Tukur D, and Alhaji AA. 2015. Contextual Factors Influencing Modern Contraceptive Use in Nigeria. DHS Working Papers No. 120. Rockville, Maryland, USA: ICF International.
 13. Sweya MN, Msuya SE, Mahande MJ, Manong R. Contraceptive knowledge, sexual behavior, and factors associated with contraceptive use among female undergraduate university students in Kilimanjaro region in Tanzania. *Adolescent Health, Medicine and Therapeutics* 2016; 7: 109115.
 14. Agyemang J, Newton S, Nkrumah I, Tsoka-Gwegweni JM, Cumber SN. Contraceptive use and associated factors among sexually active female adolescents in Atwima Kwanwoma District, Ashanti region-Ghana. *Pan Afri Med J* 2019; 32:182. Available at: doi:10.11604/pamj.2019.32.182.15344. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
 15. Monjok E, Smesny A, Ekabua, JE, Essien EJ. Contraceptive practices in Nigeria: Literature review and recommendation for future policy decisions. *Open Access J Contracept* 2010; 1: 922.
 16. Akintayo AA, Akin-Akintayo OO, Adanikin AI, Ade-Ojo IP. Sexual and Contraceptive Practices among Female Undergraduates in a Nigerian Tertiary Institution. *Ethiop J Health Sci* 2015; 25(3): 209-216. Available at: DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ejhs.v25i3.3>. (Accessed 26 February 2021).
 17. Schruppf LA, Stephens MJ, Nsarko NE, Akosah E, Baumgartner JN, Ohemeng-Dapaah O et al. Side effect concerns and their impact on women's uptake of modern family planning methods in rural Ghana: a mixed methods study. *BMC Women's Health* 2020; 20:57. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-0885-0>. (Accessed 27 February 2021).
 18. Alvergne A, Stevens R and Gurmu E. Side effects and the need for secrecy: characterizing discontinuation of modern contraception and its causes in Ethiopia using mixed methods. *Contracept Reprod Med* 2017; 2:24 Available at: DOI 10.1186/s40834-017-0052-7. (Accessed 27 February 2021).
 19. Thobani R, Jessani S, Azam I, Reza S, Sami N, Rozi S, et al. Factors associated with the discontinuation of modern methods of contraception in the low income areas of Sukh Initiative Karachi: A community-based case control

study. PLoS ONE 2019; 14(7): e0218952.

Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0218952>.

(Accessed 27 February 2021).

20. Ochako R, Mbondo M, Aloo S, Kaimenyi S, Thompson R, Temmerman M et al. Barriers to modern contraceptive methods uptake among young women in Kenya: a qualitative study. BMC Public Health 2015; 15:118. Available at: DOI 10.1186/s12889-015-1483-1. (Accessed 27 February 2021).